

Numerical Studies on the Delamination Mechanism in Laminated Composites under Impact Loading

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Abstract

This paper concerns finite element analysis of delamination failures in E-glass/epoxy composite laminate plates under impact loading. The plate concerned is a two-layered laminate plate with different fiber orientation for each layer. Explicit finite element approaches with tie-break contact interface algorithm are used to predict the interface behavior of the layers. The orientation and the normalized delamination failure stress distributions due to the impact loading are calculated to examine the delamination mechanism of the plates. The calculated delamination patterns are in good agreement with experimental observations.

1 Introduction

Fiber-reinforced composite materials are widely used in aircraft and modern vehicles. Although the composite laminates have high specific stiffness and in-plane strength, they are very susceptible to impact loading, which may cause invisible delaminations in the material. With delaminations in services, the stiffness of the material and thus that of the associated structure may be significantly reduced, which may result in a catastrophic failure of the structure. It is therefore highly desirable to estimate the delaminations in the composite materials under impact loading. A possible way to do this is, of course, to conduct physical experiments with given materials, boundary conditions, loading conditions, etc. However, physical experiment approaches have limitations. Often, they are expensive and time consuming. Thus, it is of interest to search for numerical methods to estimate possible delamination in composites subjected to impact loading.

In recent years delamination failures of composite materials have received much research efforts, e.g. in Liu [1]. However, few attempts have been made to numerically predict the orientation of delamination because the delamination failure mechanisms may be complex. In this paper the objective is to numerically investigate the delamination mechanisms of the laminated plate, including the orientation of delamination and the normalized failure stress distribution in the delamination subjected to impact loading. An explicit finite element program LS-DYNA3D, Hallquist et al. [2], with tie-break contact interface algorithm is used for this study. Solid elements are used to model the $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]$ and the $[0^{\circ}/45^{\circ}]$ E-glass/Epoxy composite laminates under impact loading. The paper is divided into five sections. After this introduction, the basic physical problem and the associated experimental results are described in the Section 2. Then, finite element modelling of the problems is discussed in Section 3. In Section 4, numerical results are presented and evaluated. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 5.

2 Problem Description and Experimental Results

The problem considered in this paper is obtained from Liu [1]. A square two-lamina plate is fully clamped at all its four edges and impacted by a steel impactor, as illustrated in Fig. 1. After being clamped around four edges, the plate has an effective dimension of 140 mm by 140 mm. The laminate plate contains two lamina, and the thickness of each lamina is 1 mm. A circular blunt-end steel cylinder of 25.4 mm in length and 9.5 mm in diameter is used as the impactor. The impactor, with mass of 14.13 grams, has a kinetic energy of 5 Joules when it hits the laminate.

Figure 1: A square two-lamina plate impacted by a steel impactor on its center

The composite laminate plates are made from E-glass/Epoxy with material constants given in $E_{11}=40$ GPa, $E_{22}=8.27$ GPa, $G_{12}=4.13$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.25$, $\rho=1900$ Kg/m³, $S_n=15$ MPa, $S_s=31$ MPa, see Aggour and Sun [3] and Agarwal and Broutman [4]. Details of the experimental set-up can be found in Liu [1].

A brief account of the experimental results, reported by Liu [1], concerning the impact delamination of the composite plate, is given as follows. The experimental results show that the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate has a peanut-like delamination shape, as illustrated in figure 2(a), whose orientation (90^0 direction) is parallel to the fiber beneath the interface, and is symmetric with respect to the x-axis and the y-axis of the plate. In the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate the orientation of the delamination is also parallel to the fiber beneath the interface, e.g. $+45^0$ directions of the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate, as illustrated in Fig. 2(b). There is no detail description about the delamination areas of this two laminate plates under impact. However, Liu has pointed out that the size of delaminated areas depends on the impactor energy. As the impactor energy increases, the interface delamination area will also increase.

Figure 2: Illustration of the peanut-like delamination profile in the interface of the (a) $[0^0/90^0]$ plate (b) $[0^0/45^0]$ plate, caused by a central impact [1].

3 Finite Element Analysis

In this study only delamination failures of the plate are of interest. Therefore, all other damages than delamination occurring in the plate may be ignored. It is not difficult to understand that an accurate modelling of the interface between the two layers is important in the analysis. Before delamination, the interface can sustain both normal stress and shear stresses up to a certain level. When delamination occurs, the interface can only sustain compressive normal and shear stresses due to friction between the two cracked layers. To model the interface behaviour, the tie-break interface algorithm in the LS-DYNA3D program, Hallquist et al., [2] will be used.

3.1 Tie-break Model

In the tie-break interface algorithm, two finite element nodes are tied together until the interaction stresses between the two nodes satisfies the following condition [2],

$$\frac{\sigma_{33}^2}{S_n^2} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2}{S_s^2} \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

where σ_{33} is the out-of-plane normal stress, σ_{23} and σ_{13} are the interlaminar shear stresses. S_n is the out-of-plane normal strength and S_s is the interlaminar shear strength. σ_{33} is nonzero for tensile values only. When the tied connection is broken, the nodes connected by the tied interface are released, accordingly. However, contact interface will still be maintained between the two nodes, which means that compressive interaction forces may be established between the nodes but not tensile forces. From the time and the position of tie-break interface failing, we can predict the initiation, propagation, size and orientation of the delamination during impact. Furthermore, we can examine how much the out-of-plane tensile stress and the interlaminar shear stresses contribute to the failure of a tie-break interface. It can be found that the tie-break interface model is similar to the delamination failure criterion as described in Chang and Springer [5].

3.2 Finite Element Model

Since the external loading, boundary conditions and material properties in the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate are all symmetric with respect to the x-axis and the y-axis, see Fig. 1, it is sufficient to only analyze one quarter of the laminate plate. The top view and side view of the finite element mesh (40x40x2) for a one-quarter of the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate are shown in Fig. 3. The shaded area is the impacted regions. Near the impacted zone, the finite element mesh is finer with element sizes of 1mm x 1mm x 1mm for the area of 20 mm x 20 mm. For the remote region, the element aspect ratio is set to 2:1 and 3:1, respectively. The impacted lamina and the non-impacted lamina are each modelled with 1600 eight-node solid elements. The element is integrated with one point integration rule. In the analysis, the interface between the impactor and the plate is modelled using a master-slave algorithm in the LS-DYNA3D program. The boundary of the impactor is taken as the master surface, and that of the laminate plate as the slave surface. No friction is assumed between the impactor and the plate. The impactor are modelled with 270 eight-node solid elements. The spurious zero-energy modes due to the reduced integration are suppressed by use of viscous form of hourglass control algorithms in the LS-DYNA3D program. The interface between the impacted lamina and the non-impacted lamina is modelled with the tie-break model.

The Chang-Chang failure criterion, see Chang and Chang [6], for composite materials is incorporated into this analysis. However, it is assumed that other damages than delamination may be ignored in the impacted plate, since we are only interested in delamination failures in this study. The solution procedure employs an explicit integration scheme based

on the central difference method. The time step size is automatically chosen smaller than the critical time step size to prevent any numerical instability.

Figure 3: The top view and side view of a one-quarter finite element mesh for the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate plate.

Concerning the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plate, we note that the material properties are not symmetric with respect to the x-axis and the y-axis. Therefore, a full FEM mesh has been used to study the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plate. In the analysis of the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plate, the total number of elements is 4 times larger than that for the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate plate. Therefore, the computational work is also four times more. The analysis of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ and the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plates have been performed on an IBM RS6000 workstation, and the main results are presented and evaluated in the following section.

4 Numerical Results and Discussions

The numerical results including the delamination patterns and the normalized failure stress distribution will be discussed below in the two separate subsections.

4.1 Delamination Patterns

The delamination patterns for the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ plate are plotted in Fig. 4. It is found that delamination first occurred at $2.3 \mu\text{s}$ at the positions given by the coordinates (0, 5) and (1, 5), which are near the edge of the impactor. A typical propagation manner of the delamination is that it starts near the edge of the impactor due to shear stresses, then it propagates along the 90° direction, and then propagate orthogonally to the 90° direction. Finally, an ellipse-like delamination shape was formed in the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate plate.

For the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ plate, the propagation of the delamination patterns are plotted in Fig. 5. The first delamination started at $2.6 \mu\text{s}$ in the position of (-4, -4) near the edge of the impactor in the direction of 225° of the plate. Then, the delamination progressed near the outside edge of the impactor due to shear stresses. It was observed that, at the interval from $4 \mu\text{s}$ to $10 \mu\text{s}$, delamination was developed mainly around the impactor or inside the impacted zone. It is not easy to find the orientation of the delamination. However, after $20 \mu\text{s}$, the delamination propagated more in the 45° and 225° directions than in the 135° and 315° directions. The orientation of the delamination shape can clearly be seen in the 45° and 225° directions for the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plate, as illustrated in Fig. 5(d).

It is noted that the orientation of delamination are parallel to the fiber direction beneath the interface in the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ and the $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$ laminate plates. Thus, the finite element calculations are in good agreement with the experiments concerning the orientation of delamination.

Figure 4: Delamination patterns for the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate at (a) $3 \mu s$ (b) $6 \mu s$ (c) $40 \mu s$ (d) $167 \mu s$. The distance between each node center is 1 mm in the x-axis and y-axis.

Figure 5: Delamination patterns for the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate at (a) $4 \mu s$ (b) $10 \mu s$ (c) $20 \mu s$ (d) $40 \mu s$. The distance between each node center is 1 mm in the x-axis and y-axis.

4.2 Normalized Failure Stress Distribution

The distribution of failure stresses in the delamination areas is an useful information to understand the failure mechanism of delamination. Thus, much attention has been paid to the calculated distribution of normalized failure stresses, which are discussed below. For convenience in discussing the distribution of failure stresses, the fiber direction beneath the interface is defined as longitudinal direction of delamination and the direction orthogonal to the fiber direction is defined as the transverse direction of delamination for the $[0^0/90^0]$ and $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plates, respectively.

Figure 6(a) shows the normalized failure stress distribution from the positions (2, 5) to (2, 19) in the longitudinal direction of the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate. At position (2, 5) near the outside edge of the impactor, the normalized tensile stress, (σ_{33}^2/S_n^2) , is zero and normalized shear stresses, $(\sigma_{13}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2)/(S_s^2)$, are 1.03 at failure. Moreover, the initiation of delamination is only caused by the normalized shear stress. However, with increasing distance from the impactor along the longitudinal direction (90^0), the effect from the normalized shear stresses decrease and the effects from the normalized tensile stress increases.

For comparison, the normalized stress at positions from (1, 5) to (11, 5) in the transverse direction (0^0) have been investigated, as shown in Fig. 6(b). The initiation and propagation of the delamination in the transverse direction (0^0) are mainly caused by the normalized shear stress, a fact indicated by zero or small values of the normalized tensile stress.

Figure 7 shows the normalized failure stress along the the delamination front in the counterclockwise direction of the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate. The normalized tensile stress are smaller than the normalized shear stresses for the angle smaller than 30 degrees. However, at the angles larger than 45 degrees, the normalized tensile stress are larger than the normalized shear stress. It indicates that the orientation of delamination in the longitudinal direction (90^0) of the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate is mainly caused by the normalized tensile stress.

The normalized failure stress distribution in the $[0^0/45^0]$ plate is also analyzed in a similar manner. Figure 8 shows the normalized failure stress for the positions from (4, 4) to (19, 19) in the longitudinal direction (45^0 direction) of the $[0^0/45^0]$ plate. At position (4, 4), the normalized tensile stress is zero and the normalized shear stresses are 1.03 at failure. However, with an increasing distance from the edge of the impactor along the longitudinal direction, the normalized shear stresses decrease and the normalized tensile stress increase. Moreover, near the tip of the delamination, the normalized tensile stress becomes more dominant in creating delamination compared to the corresponding normalized shear stresses.

From the above investigation, we can see the following two facts (1) the initiation of delamination is caused by the normalized shear stresses in the $[0^0/90^0]$ and $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plates, (2) the orientation of delamination is mainly caused by the normalized tensile stress in the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate. However, the normalized tensile stress in the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate is not much larger than the normalized shear stresses. The reason is probable that the stiffness mismatching in the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate is not so strong as in the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate.

In their numerical analysis, Sun and Grady [7] have studied the initiation of an embedded crack in the $[90^0/0^0]_{5s}$, T300/934 composite beam under impact loading. Thus, the crack extension for the mid-plane delamination can be considered as Mode II crack delamination. Sun and Grady emphasized that their analysis is valid only until the onset of initiation of delamination in the laminate. Our present analysis shows that the initiation of delamination is mainly caused by the normalized shear stresses (Mode II), which is in good agreement with Sun and Grady results.

Our analysis also shows that a high value of the normalized tensile stress (a high stiffness

Figure 6: Normalized failure stress (a) in the longitudinal direction (b) in the transverse direction of the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate.

Figure 7: Normalized failure stress counterclockwise along the delamination front in the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate.

mismatching) between the two adjacent layers, e.g. 0^0 and 90^0 , will cause the orientation of delamination along the direction of the fiber beneath the interface, which is a fact pointed out also in Liu [1].

5 Conclusions

The delamination patterns and the normalized failure stress distributions of the laminated plate under impact are studied using the finite element method. Our numerical results suggest the following conclusions.

1. The initiation of delamination is caused by the normalized interlaminar shear stresses in the $[0^0/90^0]$ and $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plates under impact. However, the orientation of the delamination is mainly caused by the normalized tensile stress in the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate. The failure mechanism in the $[0^0/45^0]$ plate is similar to that in the $[0^0/90^0]$ plate. However, the normalized tensile stress value near the tip of the delamination in the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plate is not so large as it is in the $[0^0/90^0]$ laminate plate.
2. The orientation of the delamination is parallel to the fiber direction beneath the interface in the $[0^0/90^0]$ and the $[0^0/45^0]$ laminate plates. The calculated delamination patterns are in good agreement with the experimental results. It is believed that the tie-break model

Figure 8: Normalized failure stress in the longitudinal direction of the [0°/45°] plate.

in the LS-DYNA3D program is useful in modeling delaminations in composite laminates under impact.

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